

**THE DESCRIPTIVE TRANSLATION OF GEOLOGICAL TERMS
AS THE MAIN REQUIREMENTS IN SCIENTIFIC MATERIALS FROM
ENGLISH INTO UZBEK**

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Annotation: *The article analyzes the peculiarities of translation in terminological system, especially in the sphere of geology. The main focus is emphasized on explicatory (descriptive) translation and expansion to render the meaning properly in the process of translation from English into Uzbek.*

Key words: *terms, terminological system, description translation, geology, transcription and transliteration*

The term are words or word combinations conveying which are specifically used within a certain branch of science, technology, trade, law, sports or the arts to render a specific notion to this certain sphere. Terms are often related to professionalisms and terminologies should follow the same rules and laws as the units of language for general purposes. On the contrary, exchange between terminological systems and the “common” vocabulary is quite a normal phenomenon, and it would be wrong to consider a term as something “special” and isolated. In translation of terms in any kind of spheres the main ways of translating them are as follows *transcription and transliteration*. For example, in the sphere of geology like the term **lithogenesis**– *литогенез*, but to do accurate translation, it is necessary not only to know the meaning of the terms but to link them with other words in text and to give the descriptive translation in the process like in this way **lithogenesis** (*литогенез– тоғ жинсларини ҳосил қилувчи жараён*). A translator of science texts must use only standard terms, avoiding slang or colloquial words.

For instance, **brown coal** – *қўнғир кўмир* (not *жигарранг кўмир*), **natural gas** – *табиий газ* (not *натурал газ*), **coal deposit**–*кўмир кони* (not *кўмир депозити*). Term translation depends on the register it is used in. In science, translators tend to translate as precisely as possible. Absolute equivalence of terms is a requirement in scientific translation. In other registers, term translation depends on the receptors background, and on the function the term plays in the text. [Proshina Z.G., 2008; 124-127]. As Z.Proshina claims, it is desirable that a translator avoid translating a descriptive by a transliterated (technical) term for the purpose of “showing off” knowledge. However, the descriptive technique is justified by the lack of an appropriate technical term in the source language. In English-to-Uzbek translation, in geology a more explicit character of the Uzbek language can necessitate the descriptive technique: **syngony or symmetry of crystals**–*кристалларнинг сингонияси ёки симметрияси, яъни шакли ёки кўриниши*, **ablation-** *абляция* (*музликларнинг эриши, буғланиши*), **anhedral-ангедрал** (*ўзига хос хусусиятларидан маҳрум бўлган минералнинг донсимон шакли*), **polished section-** *анилиф* (*маъданли минераллар жойлашиши ва таркибини бинокуляр остида ёки акс этган нурда кўриб ўрганиш учун сайқаллаб тайёрланган тоғ жинси намунаси*), **weathered coal**–*тошкўмирнинг нураган қолдиқлари*.

In translation of scientific and technical texts the essential task is to determine the situation described in the original. The translator should be aware of the context in order to translate correctly. The predominance of the referential function is a great challenge to the translator who must have a good command of scientific and technical terms and a sufficient understanding of the subject matter to be able to give an adequate description of the situation even if this is not fully achieved in the original. The translator is also expected to be aware of and follow the stylistic requirements of scientific and technical materials to make text acceptable to the specialist. [Bobyreva N.N., 2012; 5]. Analyzing the geological terminological system of the English and Uzbek languages as part of our study, we can conclude that in both languages, among the terms-metaphors, we can distinguish similar

grounds for they transfer of meaning. For example, the name of the equipment (object) used in the oil and gas field of geology in Russian is “*Фонтанная арматура*” and in Uzbek the term “*Фонтансимон арматура*” may be partially understandable to non-experts in the oil field, because it is taken in relation to the shape of the equipment and is semi-motivated to the type of term. is included, but the analogue of this term is called *Christmastree* in English, which makes it difficult for both terminologists and experts in the field to explain the meaning of the term and what exactly it is about. In such cases, terms are considered unmotivated, and in some cases unmotivated terms are replaced by motivated terms. For example, the term *Christmastree* can be changed to the term *Wellhead equipment*, **fishing**–*тутиши ишлари олиб бориши*, **fish** –*нефть қудуғидаги бегона предмет*, **butterfly**–*узатиши мосламаси*.

So, explicatory (descriptive) translation and expansion is a new tendency in translation theory and these techniques are used for verbalizing new objects, not existing in the target language and to reach the validity of translation.

THE LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

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